

**THE IMPACT OF THE NIGERIAN CIVIL
WAR ON URATTA COMMUNITY, IN
OWERRI NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT
AREA OF IMO STATE**

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian Civil War was not an accident of history but an inevitable consequence of the political and economic imbalance that gripped Nigeria after independence on October 1, 1960. The Nigerian Civil War devastated the people of Uratta when they were attacked after defending themselves. the measures they took backfired, leading to the capture of the community. This war caused a lot of suffering and hardship to the people. After the war, the Nigerian Federation emerged as a great nation that is indivisible with one destiny and one constitution.

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SCOPE OF STUDY

The topic “the impact of the Nigerian civil war on Urattu in the present Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State” will present us with an interpretation of the war period which lasted for about thirty months.

The impact was such that it led to loss of life and property, political instability, socio-cultural neglect and confusion, etc.

Moreso, the Igbo-dominated geopolitical zone known as Eastern Nigeria or otherwise known as Biafra suffered more from this war than any other part of the country.

However, for a clear understanding of this work, I will limit the scope to the impact of the Nigerian Civil War on the Uratta community in the present Owerri North Local Government Area from 1967-2010.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

The aim of this work is to know the political, economic and socio-cultural activities of the people of Uratta before the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war.

The objective will also be aimed at knowing the remote and immediate causes of the Nigerian civil war, its effects (positive/negative) on the people of Uratta.

Likewise, an attempt will be made to find solutions and/or recommendations for the problems caused to Uratta and its people as a result of the war.

The purpose will also be to fulfill the academic requirements for the award of a bachelor's degree in history and international studies.

ORGANIZATION OF WORK

The chapters of this work will be arranged in the following order:

CHAPTER ONE

1. A brief history of Uratta people.
 - i. Political activities of Uratta people before the war.
 - ii. Economic activities of Uratta people before the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war.
 - iii. Socio-cultural activities of Uratta people before the Nigerian civil war.

CHAPTER TWO

1. The causes of the Nigeria-Biafra civil war.
 - i. The remote causes.
 - ii. The immediate causes.

CHAPTER THREE

1. The impact of the Nigerian civil war on Uratta and its people.
 - i. Political effect.

- ii. Economic effect.

CHAPTER FOUR

Other impacts of the civil war.

- i. Socio-cultural effects.
- ii. Positive effect.

Conclusion and Recommendations

METHODOLOGY

In writing this project, both primary and secondary sources were used. The primary sources involves oral traditions/interviews of some witnesses of the civil war who are indigenes of Uratta as well as those who served in Uratta during the civil war period. The primary sources include an assessment and observation of some major theatres of war in Uratta.

Other source are secondary sources which involves published and unpublished articles, newspaper, archives, project reports of students in institutions of higher learning , text books on Nigerian civil war, web-site based access on computers etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot has been written on the Nigerian civil war by different scholars and authors from different perspectives. All have laid emphasis on the causes of the Nigerian civil war and how it claimed the lives of Nigerian innocent civilians.

Some as well wrote and highlighted the political immaturity and lopsidedness that lingered in the nation then. All these problems started even before and after the Nigerian attainment of independence on October 1, 1960. The causes of all these problems have been mainly or are traceable to the northern population who wanted to monopolize power in Nigeria.

Others have also failed to point out certain areas where innocent citizens died in large numbers in the years when the feud was existing between various regions due to one reason or the other.

Nigeria which is a fragile nation with over 280 ethnic groups is bound to curve several intractable problems, unless adequate measures are taken might lead to the disintegration of this great nation.

All these reasons that led to the collapse of the Nigerian First Republic have been advanced by so many authors and scholars.

Thus, Maduebo Alexander¹ (1980:90) argued that Nigeria was not a homogenous entity before and after independence in view of the widely differing peoples and tribes, all with different cultures. He continued that "the political struggle and the consequent drifting apart of various peoples of Nigeria went on over the years unchecked to an extent that the federal parliament was reduced to an inter-tribal battle field". He also asserted that Nigeria by 1967 was at the edge of precipice which needed only a slight push for the country to disintegrate. The causes of this was due to intolerance, corruption, ethnicity and suspicion on the part of the three major ethnic groups that make up Nigeria.

Ademoyega, Adewale² (1981:47) is of the opinion that the politisation of the top echelons of the army contributed in no small measures to the failure of their coup. This failure was to be seen in the people that lost their lives during the coup and the way the politicians were also killed. These were mostly Northerners and Westerners, while no Easterner was involved in this. The counter-coup of July 29, 1966, was organized by certain northern military officers to avenge for the massacre of their kinsmen by Major Chukwuma Kaduna Nzeogwu led coup of January 1966.

The view of Ademoyege was supported by General Olusegun Obasanjo³ (1980:105) when he posits that the war itself was the culmination of an easy pace and stability that ploughed Nigeria from independence which the country stumbled into...but the immediate causes of the civil war itself may be identified in the coup and counter-coup of 1966 which altered the political equation and destroyed the fragile trust existing among the major ethnic groups. Obasanjo explicitly pointed out that it was Colonel Ojukwu the then governor of the eastern Nigeria that was to be blamed for the outbreak of the war in 1967. This he (Obasanjo) said was because Ojukwu proved adamant and obstinate to the solutions of the Nigerian political problems. In the same vein, he also blamed the northern intellectuals and elites who are the worst peddlers of tribalism and destructive conflicts and politics for their personal aggrandisement. He as well condemned the restriction of non-indigenes in the area called sabongari in the north as it was not to the best interest of the nation.

Some scholars are of the view that the war should be blamed on Gowon who after the Aburi Accord seized the eastern regional government revenue. Gowon instead went further to impose land,

sea and air blockage against the region. This was one of the reasons that promoted the thinking of the Easterners that their survival was in their hands. Therefore, secession was necessary in order for them to save their heads. Most other writers also put that the civil war was fought to maintain the stability and solidarity of the country as a united nation. They said that without the war, there will be no peace.

J. B. Webster et al ⁴ (1980:350) refuted the ideas put up by many authors and scholars that the causes of the civil war was rooted wholly on ethnic and religious distrust between the three major ethnic groups; Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba. He based his argument on the fact that many countries which have similar divergent religious and cultures still manage to live together in harmony. He is therefore of the view that the war could have been averted if a satisfactory constitutional base is political flexibility to make it work and if an adequate economic base had been worked by our erstwhile colonial masters (Britain), the war would have probably been averted. To him, the cause of the war was that the British gave an absolute majority to one region, the political parties have become regionalized rather than nationally based and therefore self-interested and in general poor

agricultural economy the one really valuable asset for the future development, oil, lay in only one part of the country.

Fredrick Forsyth⁵ (1977:21) lended weight to Webster et al's arguments that the war was a result of the ascendancy of the northern political and economic monopoly. He cited as saying that

"During the various regional conferences summoned by macpherson during 1949, the northern delegates claimed fifty percent (50%) representation for the north and the central government and at the general conferences at Ibadan in January 1950, the Emirs of Zaria and Katsina announced that unless the northern region is allocated 50% of the seats in the central legislature, it will ask for separation from the rest of Nigeria on the arrangement existing before 1914. They got their wish and northern domination of the centre became an inbuilt future of the Nigerian politics".

Forsyth is of the view that it was the British that caused the Nigerian civil war. This he said started in 1914, when they amalgamated the north and the south thereby ending the protectorate system of administration.

According to L. M. Okafor⁶ (1980:450) the war was caused as a result of the quarrel between Ojukwu and Gowon which made their reconciliation extremely difficult.

African Concord⁷ (1978:25-34) has it that the civil war became inevitable because of the blatant refusal of Gowon to implement the Aburi agreement of many acts of atrocities against the Igbo. It is of the view that had the Aburi Accord been implemented, the civil war would have been obviated.

Another question to now ask is, "who is to be blamed for this war?" Ntienyong A. Akpan⁸ (1976:89) is assertively blaming Ojukwu and the Igbo for dragging and plunging the nation into the costly thirty (30) months civil war which halted and paralysed the socio-political and economic development of the nation within the 1967-1970 Nigeria. He pointed out that a number of reconciliatory moves had been provided whereby the differences that were existing would be resolved but Ojukwu supported by the Igbo moved ahead and proclaimed the Republic of Biafra. He therefore, argued that it was secession of the East that made the civil war inevitable. Therefore in

the need for Gowon to maintain the integrity of the nation he declared the war on Biafra.

Egbebelu Ugobelu⁹ (1994:136) maintained and debunked this view when he assertively said that:

"anybody who thinks that the war could have been avoided by the easterners coming to the bargaining table must be kidding. The twelve states structure even in it's flown nation would not have been created if the east have gone for the talks. But we must not forget that it was created as a contingency plan"

Egbebelu Ugobelu (p. 137) also mentioned as saying that:

"There could be no better "propaganda" medium than the thousands of mutilated bodies and the minds that mately or disconsolately found their ways back to the east; the story of gore, the story of mentally and sexually abused women who were held down while lepers raped them and then stuck their leprosy hands in their mouths.

This means that he debunked the ideas of Ademoyege and Obasanjo where they assertively maintained that all blamed the Igbo and ultimately Ojukwu for the war. These people (Obasanjo and

Ademoyega) implied that Ojukwu was a tyrant and that his ambition to rule caused him to use his efficient propaganda machine to whip up the people's sentiment to a frenzy, thereby not giving them any other alternative than go to war. Therefore, Agbebelu Ugobelu is of the idea that propaganda was a novel and had only a marginal contribution to the overall war favour. This for nothing had the effect of bolstering the courage of Biafrans, who literally had nothing to fight with but to defend themselves with whatever they had in hand like providing themselves with fuel, rifles, mortars etc.

According to Boniface Egboke¹⁰ of Post Expressions, anyone who decides to fight a war because of mineral resources or religion can hardly lose or stop fighting such a war until success is achieved as recent and ancient history can easily confirm. The Nigerian Biafran war was fought solely for self-determination and was lost because it was mismanaged when saboteurs stormed the Biafran enclave and hunger was used as a weapon of war. The painful events of that war are still very clear on every body's mind and cannot be wished away. The causes of that war are still around. The injustices that brought about the war are all over Nigeria. If anything, more people have now understood the plight of the Igbo and the so-called minorities of the

east who were embroiled in that useless war. He went further to state that what caused that war are still very clear in my mind; some I did learn from my elders, and some I did see and witnessed by myself. The issues arising from the Nigerian-Biafran war are a composite of a sacred duty that affected many lives of Nigerians, and that still affect many today. There are a lot of lessons to be learnt from that experience. They are events that must be handled with care for the present, future, prosperity and history. The lives of our heroes past must never be in vain.

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CHAPTER ONE

A BRIEF HISTORY OF URATTA PEOPLE

Uratta is the largest community in Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. It is bounded on the north by Mbaitoli Local Government, on the south by Ihitte Ogada and Awaka, on the east by Ikeduru and on the west by Owerri Nchi-Ise.

Though there are diverse tales of origin, most of the Uratta people appeared to have lived in their present home from the dawn of history. Archaeological evidence suggest that the Uratta people have lived in their present homeland for a very long period.

However, it was gathered that Uratta first settled at Orié Uratta (Orié Uratta Market Square). He gave birth to two sons: Obibi the first and Ihitaoha. Obibi had four(4) sons, namely according to their seniority, Alum, Orii, Obaa and Okwu. Also Ihitaoha had four(4) sons namely according to their seniority-Owalla.Owaelu, Umunahu and Orji. These children make up the eight(8) villages in Uratta (UrattaOfo asato) namely- Umualum, Umuorii.Umuoba, Okwu, Owalla,Owaelu, Umunahu and Orji.

But as a result of Population explosion and migration, they now settled in ten villages (Uratta Ofo Iri) these two villages that make up the ten village in Uratta are Amakohia and Akwakuma Uratta. These two villages have their origins from Owelu and Umunahu .

We cannot discuss Uratta without mentioning "Eshimesh Ohii." people as they migrated from Umunahu to their Present settlement and this accounts for why they cannot marry from Umunahu. The Eshimeshi Ohii people also celebrate the Onwa-oru which is the yearly festival of Uratta people.¹

Uratta is said to have brothers among whom are Ihitte Ogada, Awaka, Egbu, Naze, Obibiezena, Obube,Agbala and Owerri Nchi- ise who migrated from Ndumoha compound, descendants of Orii Uratta. Ekwema was said to have fled for safety due to misunderstanding between him (Ekwema) and Ndumoha and finally settled at a place known today as Ugwu Ekwema, between Egbu and the present Owerri Nchi-lsi town from where he extended to other areas known today as Owerri town²

In view of the above, Uratta is seen and respected as the first son among these other villages including Owerri town. This makes account

for the popular saying "Owerri wu Owerri wu Uratta". (Owerri originated from Uratta). It is also imperative to mention that Uratta and his brothers do not eat a particular specie of yam known as "Una"³

The fact that Uratta migrated and settled in their present homeland was not because they were ever dislodged from their homeland by physical disasters, or as a result of dramatic and traumatic external intervention.

One account of the historical origin of the Uratta people has it that Uratta migrated from Arochukwu Ohafia to their present homeland..

This account has it that Uratta was a great hunter and a Native doctor who wandered in search of food and to escape from the wrath of the gods and finally settled at "Orie" Uratta.

Another account of the historical origin of Uratta people has it that Uratta migrated from Atta Ikeduru and finally found his place of abode in "Orie" Uratta. Uratta was wandering from place to place hunting for food and animals, searching for water and suitable place for settlement. During his nomadic years of life, he took shelter on caves and under certain trees. Of all these trees that gave him shelter, he enjoyed and cherished the Obu tree most. Hence he esteemed the "Obu" tree above all other trees for it's shelter till date.

Also, a similar account of such migration was traced to Uratta Ngwa. This also has it that Uratta may have migrated from Ngwa in the present Abia State. This account said that Uratta was an indigene of Ngwa, a rain maker and a native doctor who was suffering so much in Ngwa and as a result decided to wander in search of a suitable place for settlement and finally found "Orie" Uratta as his place of abode. One of the back-up of this account was that neither Uratta nor Uratta Ngwa can marry each other because no one knows the exact village from Uratta Ngwa where Uratta migrated from so as not to marry brothers and sisters.⁴

i. POLITICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE URATTA PEOPLE BEFORE THE CIVIL WAR

In the pre-civil war Uratta, political activities/authorities rested on the heads of the villages who were invariably the eldest men. Each village head was called "Onye-Ishi Ala". Each village was also sub-divided into lineages called "Umunna" headed by the eldest man called "Okenye Umunna". When a matter affected the whole Uratta Community, "Ndi-Ishi Ala" (village heads) would meet and deliberate on the matter. Each village head would then carry the message home and discuss with the

various kindred where all "adult males and every aged women" were entitled to attend and participate. A similar process was repeated in the lineage where the "Okenye Umunna' would preside ⁵

Among the Uratta people, two layers of political structures are identified: the village and the village groups, with the village structure being the most powerful. At the compound level, authority revolved around the head of the compound called "Onye-nwe-ezi". It was his responsibility to shield members of his compound from any external attack. In return all members of the compound were under obligation to accord him the respect he deserved which included giving him palm wine at every "Orie Uratta" market day.

From the level government moved to the lineage which could be described as a group of compounds tracing their descendents to one ancestor. Here the authority rested with the "Okpara", the first male born child who at the same time held the staff of authority known as "ofo". It was he who controlled the affairs of the entire lineage, interceding between the lineage members and the ancestors and also representing the lineage in all matters in the next level of government in the village.

As it was said earlier, the village was the highest political authority in Uratta. Here, there was direct democracy. All lineages participated in the affairs of the village and the institution of government including the village assembly called "Amala" made up of all male adults. Within this assembly revolved all legislative, judicial, administrative and executive functions.

In the gathering of the village assembly all matters were thrown open to general discussion and all present were free to contribute their ideas. After the deliberations the leaders of the lineage retired into what was called "Igba Izu" (consultation) after which a spokesman announced the verdict. The village assembly was free to accept or reject the decisions arrived at "Izu". If the decisions was accepted by the whole "Amala" the "ofo" holders sanctioned it and it became law.

Among the matters the Uratta village legislated upon where the control and regulation of economic affairs, making of war, and concluding of peace and defence. This is evident in the land dispute between Umunahu Uratta and Uzogba in Ikeduru local government area.

The next level of government in Uratta was the village group which was a representative association of villages. It had no defined power except

on matters affecting the earth goddess and common institutions like market or roads.⁶

Members of the Uratta were so organized that an individual defaulter or law-breaker was ostracized as precaution against divine vengeance.

It is very unfortunate to observe that with the incursion of the colonial masters followed by the outbreak of the Nigeria-Biafran civil war in 1967, the political activities/organization of Uratta people gradually gave way to the authority of the wealthy. These were people who were rich enough to take the highest titles in Uratta community. Such titles taking ranged from "Onye-Ishi Oha", "Oji ofo", "Onye Oha" — and Ada Uratta etc. The prerequisite for the possession of these titles moved from age to wealth. The rich titled men became the governing council in Uratta community and now seem to have taken over the functions of the elders. The new wealthy titled men became known as "Ndi Amadi" as against the "Ichie" Ogbenye or poor elder. "Ndi Amadi now began to initiate village council meetings which were formally the prerogative of the elders. And in those meetings, the contributions made by a wealthy titled man (age notwithstanding) was more agreeable to those present than that of the poor elder no matter if he was the poor eldest⁷.

However, it must be concluded that no matter the shift of authority or power from the "Ichie's" to the wealthy men, Uratta had and is still maintaining its organized political setting and this accounts for the reason why Uratta community holds a pride of place among her brothers or neighbours. And to this day recognized by government hence the citing of Owerri North Local Government heauquarters in Orië Uratta.

ii. ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES OF THE URATTA PEOPLE BEFORE THE OUTBREAK OF THE NIGERIAN CIVIL WAR

Farming and hunting were the dominant occupations of the Uratta people in pre-civil war period. The instruments of farming labour were hoes, axes, spades and metals. While the instruments for hunting includes bows and arrows, carterpults, dane gun (egbe ntu) etc. Muscular energy was necessary for handling these implements. It was the duty of the men to clear and burn the farm lands and later break up the soil into mounds for women to plant the traditional food crops -Yam, Cocoyam, Melon, Maize, Pumpkin etc.

In pre-civil war period of Uratta, farming was carried for both subsistence and commercial purposes. Land tenure was governed by the principle that land belongs to the community as a whole, and that by birth right,

every individual would have security for the cultivation of basic foodstuff. Every members of the society in Uratta had the right to land. Farming in Uratta community is carried out only after the celebration of "Onwa-Oriu Uratta" yearly festival (1st week in February).

However, what is clear is that the existing mode of economic activities of the Uratta people especially working the land, constituted the pivot of the nomadic system of the Uratta people. Days of week for instance, were known in terms of their relationship to farming, marketing of crops and hunting. Seasons had a bearing to periods of cultivation and harvest in Uratta. Historical landmarks were fixed by reference to unusual occurrences such as eclipse; or by reference to great inter-communal war. Feasts were celebrated on specific days for gods of the land. Members of the Uratta are so organically linked that an individual defaulter or law breaker was ostracized as precaution against divine vengeance.

Also given the unrestricted access to land-resources, each individual in Uratta could afford three square meals. Begging was tabooed in Uratta. Extended family system provided for the naturally incapacitated. Polygamy was also encouraged in pre-civil war Uratta as women were not only partners in biological reproduction but also associates in

economic production. In relation to the labour intensive mode of production, increased family strength was always an asset rather than a liability in pre-civil war period of Uratta.⁸

Uratta people also indulged in buying and selling before the outbreak of the Nigeria-Biafra civil war. Products of their harvest were taken to markets for sale so as to make money to buy other essentials of life. Some of the markets where these goods were taken include - Ekemegbuoha, Nkwo Umuobaa, Orié Umuorri, Afor Okwu, Eke Atta, Ekeukwu Owerri, Afor Inyogwugwu etc.

Similarly, Uratta people also involved themselves in animal husbandry. Such animals includes: goats, fowls, dogs, sheep etc.

However, it must be stated that yam was the main staple food crop of Uratta people before the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war in 1967.⁹

iii. SOCIO-CULTURAL ACTIVITIES OF URATTA PEOPLE BEFORE THE NIGERIAN CIVIL WAR

According to Ndoh (1997:66) culture has been an institution, where ideas, beliefs, skills, tools, methods of thinking, as well as custom of each member of the society are born.

However, culture has basic institutions, such as the family for training the child, which influences personality, festivals for regulating the calendar, relaxation and entertainment. This is why it is popularly said that a community or town without its own culture or social activities is like a person without a name.

The socio-cultural activities of Uratta people include above all "Onwa Oru" Uratta festival which is celebrated at the first week of February every year to mark the beginning of a planting season and end of harvest season. The venue for this festival is the "Orie Uratta" market square. The activities of this festival includes presentation of each first daughter of Uratta family before the people of Uratta or ancestors (Ibi ukwu obu), masquerades, cultural dances, music bands, wrestling, football, and other recreational activities.

Another socio-cultural activity of Uratta people before the war was chieftaincy title taking such as "Ichi Nze na Ozo", "Ichi Ozu", "Ichi "Onye isi ala", "Ichi Onye Isi Ofo", "Ichi Onye Isi Oha", "Ichi Ada" Uratta, " Ichi Eze" etc. All these title taking activities were carried out on a particular market day. (Orie). On that day, friends, relatives and well wishers are invited to grace these memorable occasions.

Moreso, "Omugwo", "Ipa Mmii ukwu nwanyi", "Hi ozu" where also the socio-cultural activities of Uratta people before the outbreak of the civil war.

However, it is important to note that of all the socio-cultural activities in Uratta, the Onwa Oru Uratta festival is about the surviving traditional/cultural festival in Uratta. According to remembered history, Onwa Onu Uratta is essentially a harvest thanksgiving festival celebrated in pomp and pageant to give thanks to the Supreme God and ancestors for the abundance of harvest.

This festival furnishes the basis for social solidarity and unity in Uratta, it stores the social heritage and values of the people, it guides the societal behaviour of the people of Uratta, it attracts tourism in Uratta, it gives Uratta people a sense of belonging and legal entity, it creates a peaceful environment within the period prior to the celebration as people are asked or instructed not to fight, women are asked not to starve their husbands or cry at night etc, and above all it serves as an avenue for learning leadership and political skills, laws, taboos and regulations.¹⁰

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CHAPTER TWO

THE CAUSES OF THE NIGERIA-BIAFRA (CIVIL) WAR

Historically speaking, before 1900, there was no geopolitical entity called Nigeria. What later came to be known and called Nigeria was a British make-up. In 1900, Lady Flora Shaw who later became Lady Lugard coined the area watered by the Niger "Nigeria", and from that period onwards, there came to be effective British occupation of Nigeria.

The causes of the Nigeria-Biafra civil war are traceable to the British who in 1914 amalgamated the Northern and Southern protectorates. The need for the amalgamation were based on administrative convenience and uniformity to the British - at least on paper. By the word "amalgamation", we mean a fusion or a merging together of two previously different entities. Thus the amalgamation of 1914 was viewed by the Northern politicians as the mistake of 1914. This was because there was not much that was different in the method and style of administration in the Northern and Southern components of the country after the exercise¹.

Nicholson, who wrote on the administration of Nigeria from 1900 - 1960 says "Easily the most remarkable thing about Lugard's administration of

Nigeria is that it never really took place from two : different bridge-heads and was executed by two different teams, Messrs. Beecroft, Glover, Carter and Moor took over Southern Nigeria for Great Britain using Lagos, Opobo and Benin as their bridge-heads. They encountered diverse people who spoke different languages and had different cultures. Indeed, these people were either strangers to one another or at perpetual warfare with one another.

On the other hand, Messrs: Goldie, Balke and Lugard, started from River Niger entered the Savanna lands of the Northern component and acquired Fulani Sokoto caliphate for Great Britain. This component was more populous than the Southern component but the vast majority of the people there spoke the same language, had the same basic culture and adhered to the same religion²

The causes of the Nigerian civil war sprang from the carefree manner in which the British took over, administered, and abandoned the government and people of Nigeria. The British administration did not make an effort to wield the country together and unite the heterogeneous groups of people. This does not imply that the British administration did nothing good in Nigeria. Far from it. Many things stand to their credit, and it is clear that present-day Nigeria owes certain

achievements to the spade work of British administration. Nevertheless, there was one evil that outlived British administration, namely, political non-advancement.

When the British came to Nigeria as an imperial nation to take over the administration or rulership of the country from 1861 (with the cession of Lagos) they met the people of the South totally free, only observing and regulating their own monarchies and institutions. But in the North the British met the Fulani in their process of establishing their rulership in most parts, except in the Kanuri area in the North-East.

From this, we can easily understand why there was a fundamental difference between the political aspirations of the leaders of the North and the South. In the South, political leadership sprang from the people, that is, from the grass-roots. The people had been the custodian of their own civic rights before the British came. It was easy and natural for the common people to be active again, when political agitation for national freedom became a popular pre-occupation of Nigerians in 1940s. In the North, however, the ruling class made up of the sons and kinsmen of the Emirs, took over the political leadership of the people. Unfortunately, they represented their own interests, rather than the popular will of the masses. This happened because the British governed Nigeria indirectly

through their traditional rulers. In the South, they governed through the Obas, Obis and Amanyabos who were relatively powerless amongst their people. In the North, they governed through the Emirs whose sons and kinsmen were the Chiefs and Native Authority Officials, who lorded it over the people. These emerged as the aristocratic political leaders of the 1940s.³

Thus in trying to solve the problems of administering such a vast territory with only a handful of British officials, the policy of "Indirect Rule" therefore emerged as the simple solution under those circumstances. At first it was adopted tentatively; but the more it was tried, the happier Lugard felt with results especially in the North. Eventually, he built this policy, which originally was a pragmatic improvisation into a lofty doctrine⁴

The introduction of Regionalism by the Richards constitution of 1945 was one of the causes of the political problems in Nigeria. This constitution was what watered the seeds of Regionalism, the disease that killed Nigeria. The three regional states were the worst of all possible worlds, once the attitude of the North had been ascertained, an attempted marriage of the irreconcilable. The North did not in any way make it secret of their separatist wish.⁵

After Richard's constitution came Sir MacPhersons who introduced a new virtually unitary state. The North had learned that it could get its way by threatening to pull out of Nigeria. During the various constitutional conferences summoned by MacPherson, the Emirs of Zaira at Katsina announced that "unless the Northern Regions were allotted fifty percent (50%) of the seats in the central legislature, it will ask for separation from the rest of Nigeria on the arrangement existing before 1914". They got their wish, and Northern domination at the centre became an inbuilt feature of Nigerian politics. They also demanded and got the loosest possible form of federation and made no secret of their deep conviction that the amalgamation of the North and the South in 1914 was an error. This expression of their conviction runs right through the Northern political thinking from the end of the World War II to independence. In 1953, the Northern political leader, Sir Ahmadu Bello told the House in Lagos "the mistake of 1914 had come to light and I should like it to go no further".⁶

The opposition of the North to the amalgamation with the South gave rise to voices of numerous statements by the Northern leaders and Malam Abubakar Tafawa Belewa who later become the Prime Minister of Nigeria said "we do not want, Sir, our Southern neighbours to

interfere in our development...! should therefore make it clear to you that if the British quitted Nigeria now at this stage, the Northern people would continue their uninterrupted conquest of the sea". Throughout the decades of the British rule in Nigeria, the Northern speeches revealed a steadily growing dislike for the Easterners in their minds. Time and time again, speakers of the Northern House voiced out their deep conviction that the "North" was for the Northerners and the South should go. In the North in 1945, spadic violence had occurred against the Easterners and it is called the Bloody Jos Riot of 1945.⁷

The origin of national anti-Igbo feeling and resentment is as old as Nigeria and quite as complicated. Igbo were the last group to be subdued by the British colonial powers (special credit to Arochukwu people) Igbo were also up on their feet earlier than others to agitate for the independence of Nigeria which was achieved on 1st October, 1960.⁸

Before Nigeria stumbled into independence, she went through series of constitutions through which she finally gained her independence from the British. The provisions of these constitutions made possible the formation of political parties and the first political party to be formed was the National Congress of Nigeria Citizens (NCNC) in 1944s whose leader was Nnamdi Azikiwe. Due to the fact that the party was

dominated by the Igbo politicians, it was termed as the Igbo, party and so was there for the protection of the interests of the Igbo. But it has to be noted that this party was the only national party.

In 1950, Awolowo, the Western leader turned a cultural organization in the West known as Egbe Omo Oduduwa founded in 1948 to a political party with the name Action Group (AG). This party was for the West and so the protection of the Western interest was its ultimate goal.

The Islamic and aristocratic Hausa-Fulani tribes of North in 1951 turned the cultural organization in the North known as the Jamya Mutanem, Ariwa to a political party with the name Northern Peoples Congress (NPC). This party was also not a national party as it was there to protect the interest of the North. This was the beginning of ethnic politics in Nigeria.⁹

At independence, the British not willing to leave were not happy with the Igbo for spearheading the struggle that brought an end to colonial authority in Nigeria. However, in order to retain their influence and keep open the continued exploitation by them of Nigeria's economy, the colonial government before bringing down their flag did conspire with the North deliberately to draw up a political map of Nigeria that gave

absolute political advantage to the North. In that map, the country was divided into three regions: the Eastern region, the Northern region and the Western region. And going by the sizes, the division was lopsided in that the Northern region alone was drawn to have as much as three quarter (3/4) of the land area of the country. The enormous landmass allocated to the North created enormous assumption of greater population and its numerical advantage for political power. The reason was to emasculate the surging wisdom and political power of the Igbo.

Before the departure of the colonial authority in 1960, Igbo were seen as catching up with the white-man's eyes of wisdom and development. For the purpose of holding down the progress of the Igbo, the forces of imperialism set up structures to promote anti-Igbo feelings in the North. The B. B. C. Hausa programme was the institutional organ through which the North received and was receiving morning and evening lessons from the British on the political situation in Nigeria and how the North should see that Igbo and react to them. It was the organ used by the British to remote-control the Nigeria-political system and politicians.

10

The last phase of drift appeared to have started with the 1959 federal election, for it was then that the political rift in the country between the

leaders of the Northern Peoples Congress, the Sarduana of Sokoto and the leader of Action Group, Chief Obafemi Awolowo dominated the political life of the country.

By 1962, the controversy had become virtually uncontrollably and thus a major threat to the very existence of Nigeria as a nation, despite genuine attempts made by Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, the then Governor-General of the federation, to reconcile them. Chief S. L. Akintola, the Premier of the Western Nigeria had earlier in the year been expelled from the A.G. for his alleged anti-part activities beneficial to the Northern Peoples Congress and the Sarduana of Sokoto. He (Chief S. L. Akintola) was replaced by Chief Adegbenro. The confused situation that followed disorganized the Action Group and appeared to have neutralized Chief Obafemi Awolowo on a permanent basis.¹¹

The basis for the Nigerian politics after independence was the struggle among the political parties to control the Federal Government. Nigeria become independent with a federal structure which within two years was shaken by an emergency, within five years, had broken down in disorder, to be finally overthrown by the two military coups and civil war.

In May 1962, there was a head-count in Nigeria but its result was never officially published. The figures obtained for the various regions were believed to have been inflated. At a meeting of the Prime Ministers and the Regional Premiers on February 10, 1963, they decided to cancel the result and repeat the exercise in November 1963. Various measures were taken to check irregularities.

The official figures which were published on August 29, 1964 put the population of the country at 55.6 million, distributed as follows:

Northern Nigeria	- 29,758,875
Eastern Nigeria	- 12,394,462
Western Nigeria	- 10,265,846
Mid-Western Nigeria	- 2,535,839
F.C.T. of Nigeria	- 0,665,246

The N.P.C - dominated federal government accepted the result, so did the governments of the Northern and Western Nigeria but the N.C.N.C. controlled government of the Eastern and Mid-Western Nigeria -ejected it, alleging that the figures attributed to the Northern Region had been inflated to "ridiculous proportion". What was left of the Action Group as a party also rejected the result.

The Eastern Nigerian government challenged the result in the court, claiming that the inflation of the figures for the Northern Nigeria would adversely affect the legal rights of Eastern Nigeria with regard to delamination of electoral constituencies and monetary grants from the federal government. This case filed by the then Head of the Eastern Regional government, Dr. Michael Okpara got nothing from the suit because the supreme court dismissed it on the ground that it lacked jurisdiction to entertain the case. Hence the relationship between N.P.C. and N. C. N. C. soured, as accusations and counter-accusations of tribalism and corruption provoked tension. This census controversy helped to show how much regional interests divided the two coalition partners in the federal government.

On December 30, 1964, Nigeria held its first post-independence general election. The allocation of seats according to the 1963 census results was as follows: North -167; East -70; West - 57; Mid-West -14; and the Federal Capital Territory of Lagos - 4; that is 145 seats in the South as against 167 in the North.¹²

In this general election, all these political parties formed two alliances - The Nigeria National Alliance (N.N.A.) and the United Progressive Grand Alliance (U.P.G.A). This election was boycotted because the

candidates of the U.P.G.A. was molested and beaten by the NPC party thugs on their campaign in the North. Up till that last moment, it was in doubt, whether there would be any election at all. In the end, it held and not unnatural, the result was in favour of N.N.A. This resulted to crisis and President Azikiwe unhappy about the constitutional position, asked Balewa to form a broad based national government and the crisis was averted that might have broken the federation in 1964. ¹³

In 1965, the chain of political events which started since 1962 reached its climax. This time the Nigerian National Democratic Party (N.N.D.P) had been formed out of the Action Group (A.G.) and its leader was Chief S. L. Akintola and backed by Sarduana of Sokoto (NPC) Premier of the Northern Region was accused of rigging the elections in the Western House of Assembly. In this election, the Nigerian National Democratic Party and the United Progressive Grant Alliance opposed each other and civil order became impossible to be restored. Infact, the Western Nigeria election crisis in 1965 was certainly the last straw against the democratic experiment of the First Republic.

To give an impression of normalcy to the world at large, the Nigerian Government called a Commonwealth Prime Minister's Conference in Lagos on January 1966. In this conference, the problem of Nigerian

unity was not discussed instead what was discussed was the Rhodesian problem. This action ignited a time fuse which was to spark off the Nigeria powder keg before long.

Unfortunately, the federal government did not show sufficient concern for the horror and carnage unleashed in the region, thereby giving the military the pretext for intervening and bringing the regime of Sir AbubakarTafawa Balewa to an abrupt end. This political situation in the country gave some young military officers the immediate pretext to stage the January 15, 1866 coup.

In this coup, their was the elimination of the political leaders and high-ranking Army officers, a ma ority of whom came from a particular section of the country (North). This made the coup to be perceived by the Northerners as having an ethnic colour. ¹⁵

The demise of the First Republic was not a surprise to many Nigerians and politicians elsewhere who, unlike, Niven, did not see the regime as "an example of what a well balanced modern African, democracy should be." It is even an abuse of language to refer to the first Republic as a democratic because there is much more to democracy anywhere is the world than the presence of a duly elected representative civilian

government. It has to be a civilian government that allows for free and fair elections, which was not the case, as illustrated in the federal election of 1964 and Western Regional election of 1965 in which the practically naked form of electoral abuse showed that the ruling parties even refused to contemplate the possibility of failure at the poles. It has to be a civilian government which does not coerce and oppress oppositions through various means, which was not the case in all the regions where the government party saw itself as the "Protector and Projector of ethnic personality", and constituencies which supported opposition members of the legislature were denied basic amenities. It has also to be a civilian government in which the electoral commission and the judiciary are fully independent, and the rule of law is scrupulously observed, which was not in the case of the First Republic because the complicity of the Federal Electoral Commission and the law court in the federal and regional elections was undeniable.

In short, the Nigerian political elites lacked the positive values and attitudinal traits which were indispensable to the operation of a democratic system of government. The consequent of this was disastrous, that is the January 15, 1966 Military coup d'etat which overthrew the first Nigerian Republic.

The coup, like the system of Indirect Rule in colonial Nigeria, was successful in the North, partially successful in the West but unsuccessful in the East. Notably, it failed in Enugu, Benin and Lagos. It was believed to have been executed in a haste in order to pre-empt an alleged complot by some Military Officers and politicians to instigate a rebellion in the Ijaw area of Eastern Nigeria which would have had the effect of diverting the attention of the N.C.N.C - led Eastern Nigerian Governor from Western Nigeria, thereby calling Chief S. L. Akintola to consolidate his hold on power there.

The failure of the coup in Lagos enabled Major General J. T. U. Aguyi-Ironsi, General Officer commanding the Nigerian Armed Forces, to take control over the situation with the assistance of some loyal troops. The motives of the January 15, 1966 coup were:

- a. neo-colonialist exploitation of the country by foreign investors and capitalists controlling major sectors of the country's economy with the connivance of politicians
- b. the structural imbalance of the country which gave the North a virtual in-built control of the legislature and other institutions, hence the unfriendly relations among the regions; and

the dominant party phenomenon in the region which made it dangerous for any region to be excluded from the federal government or discriminated against because each region had a population large enough to become a sovereign state. It was as a result of this coup that on January 16, 1966, the acting President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Dr. Nwafor Orizu (President of the Senate), handed over the administration of the country to the Armed Forces through Major Gen. Aguyi-Ironsi, hence he was formally invested with authority as Head of the Federal Military Government and Supreme Commander of the Nigerian Armed Forces. The coup was welcomed by the Nigerian public, the press, and the educated elites including the Northerners. But it was through the B.B.C. Hausa programme that the British gave Hausas a wrong picture of the intentions of the coup leaders which led to serious suspicion by the North of the subsequent administrative policies of the Ironsi regime as he was alleged of surrounding himself with Igbo advisers and trying to establish Igbo hegemony in the country. ¹⁶

When General Ironsi became the Head of State, he promulgated a decree which abolished federalism and introduced unitarism. This means that Nigeria will be run like a unitary state. Thus this decree was widely interpreted by the North as an attempt to bring that region under

Southern control. This development prepared the ground or stage for a counter-coup on July 29, 1966 by the Northern Military officers. In this coup, Major General J. T. U. Aguyi-Ironsi, Adekunle Fajuyi and other Igbo military officers and politicians lost their lives.

At the end of the coup, the troops that led that coup decided to choose General Gowon as the Military Head of State. But the mantle of leadership passing to Gowon was contested by Ojukwu because Gowon was a junior military officer.

On September 1966, there was the massacre of the Igbo in the North. Ojukwu the then Governor General of the Eastern Region reacted by calling all Easterners in all parts of the federation to return to the Eastern region. He also expelled all non-Easterners in the East and therefore prepared for the secession of the East from the federation.¹⁷ As these events were going on, General Ankrah, the then Military Head of Ghana succeeded in arranging in meeting whereby the differences that existed between Gowon and Ojukwu could be amicably resolved without necessarily resulting to the use of arms and ammunitions.

At the Ghana conference held in Aburi, on January 4 and 5, 1967, under the auspices of the Ghanaian Head of State, General Ankrah, present were:

Lt. Col. Yakubu Gowon, Head of the Federal Military Government

Col. Robert Adebayo, Military Governor of Western Nigeria

Lt. Col. C. O. Ojukwu, Military, Governor of Eastern Nigeria.

Lt. Col. H. U. Katsina, Military Governor of Northern Nigeria

Lt. Col. D. O. Ejoor, Military Governor of Mid-Western Nigeria.

Also present were four other members of the supreme military council.

At this meeting, Ojukwu scored a diplomatic victory which made the federal government almost impotent. Gowon was thus called upon by the Northern leaders to resist or revoke the agreement reached at Aburi. The decision reached at Aburi was that Nigeria should be run as a confederation. Paradoxically, the Aburi Accord intensified the conflict that it was meant to resolve. The reason is that Gowon at Aburi accepted appropriated all federal revenue realized in the region in order to finance the rehabilitation programme decided at Aburi. The edicts nullified the normal procedure for sharing federal collected revenue

b) The legal education edict, and

c) The Court of Appeal Edicts; by virtue of which the legal system of Eastern Nigeria became autonomous.

Of the three edicts, it was only the one on revenue collection that Ojukwu justified with the following reasons:

- i. The failure of the Federal Military Government to pay salaries to refugee civil servants and corporation employees up to March 31, 1967, as agreed to at Aburi.
- ii. Eastern Nigeria need to cater for and rehabilitate some 1.8 million people whose displacement from other parts of Nigeria was irreversible; and
- iii. The federal government delay in paying to the East its statutory share of revenue and the withholding of monies due to the region

The reaction of the federal government was to immediately blockade the Eastern Region, severing all postal and communication links between it and the rest of the federation. In addition, it placed an embargo on exchange transactions in favour of the region. In refuting Ojukwu's charges, the federal government claimed to have already given a grant to N700.000 to Eastern Nigeria for the rehabilitation of its displaced persons. Ojukwu did not get any such grant and doubted very much that

it was actually released because the belief in Lagos was that he could use any money given to the region (East) to buy arms.

Lt. Col. Ojukwu became even more defiant. In April 1967, he regionalized federal institution and properties in the East, such as the Ports Authority, Post and Telegraphs, Nigerian Railway Corporation, Coal Corporation and the Nigeria Broadcasting Corporation. What remained to be done was to declare the region as a sovereign state. But it was already a "de facto" independent state.

In a bid to check the widening gulf between the two principle actors in the crisis, a National Conciliation Committee comprising some prominent Nigerians like Sir Adetokumbo Ademola, Chief Justice of the Federation, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, and Chief F. Mariere, Adviser to the Military Governor of Eastern Nigeria on March 5, 1967. Their discussion with Lt. Col. Ojukwu left them in no doubt that the East would accept nothing less than a confederal political structure for Nigeria which would enable it lick its wounds in relative "quarantine" and avoid any friction with the North. It was therefore unthinkable that Ojukwu would revoke the edicts by which he unilaterally implemented the Aburi Accord if the federal government lifted the restrictions on communications and foreign exchange transactions imposed against the East.

In reality, the crux of the matter was not Ojukwu's edicts or Gowon's sanctions but their disagreement on the Aburi decisions. In any case, in spite of the federal government's sanction against the East, Ojukwu was still getting informations from Lagos on the directions which Gowon's advisers were urging him to go. For instance, Ojukwu knew that the creation of more states by the federal government was suggested as the best political strategy to "clip his wings" and that Gowon was not only attracted to the idea but was also actually going to promulgate a decree to that effect before long. He also knew that two of the new states were to be carved out of Eastern Nigeria and that the objective was to confine the Igbo to a territory which excluded most of the oil wells, even if that meant separating some of the Igbo from their kith and kin, as was results from Ikwere people being included in the River State. That was why on April 24, 1967, - 33 days before the federal government created 8 new states - he (Ojukwu) summoned diplomatic representatives to Enugu and said.:

"If Lagos carries out it's proposal, it will mean they no longer accept the East as part of Nigeria. The path open to us in that event is clear and I shall have no alternative but to take it."

On May 26, he summoned a joint meeting of the consultative Assembly, Chiefs, and Elders of the region and addressed them at length on the developments in the "struggle". The meeting accordingly mandated him to "declare, at the earliest practicable date, Eastern Nigeria free, sovereign and independent state by the name and title Republic of Biafra".

On May 27, 1967, Gowon created the new states bringing the numbers of federating states to 12, viz:

Northern Nigeria -	North Eastern state.
	North Central State
	Kano State
	Northern Western State
	Benue - Plateau State.
Eastern Nigeria -	East Central State
	South Eastern State
	River State
Western Nigeria -	Western State
	Lagos State

Mid-Western Nigeria Mid-West State (no change)

The next day he (Gowon) repeated Decree No.8 (Aburi Decree), the structural reorganization of the federation having rendered it obsolete. To Lt. Col. Ojukwu, that was the last straw. The dyes was cast. He had earlier on warned that the Eastern Region would secede if there was any interference with its territorial integrity. Undaunted by these developments, Ojukwu on May 30 1967, pulled the Eastern Region out of the Nigeria federation. ¹⁸

When the Eastern Region declared itself a sovereign nation called Biafra, neither side anticipated a war. Biafra was optimistic that Nigeria would not fight to keep them in the federations since thousands of them were killed in the program preceding that declaration. Nigeria for their part did not look at it as a worth while project fighting against Eastern secession since according to Gowon himself, there was no existing basis for unity in Nigeria.

But like thunderbolt, the British government warned the North against the economic consequences and dangers to them of allowing the Eastern Region to secede from Nigeria. This warning was because the imperialistic forces knew that great economic resources are located down there in Igboland, and there would be no room for further foreign

exploitation. They promised providing support and mobilizing international military assistance to Nigeria against Biafra. On the diplomatic front, the British also mobilized international opinion to lie again Biafra as seceding in order to recolonize their minority neighbours in the Eastern Region. The slogan "to keep Nigeria one is a task that must be done" was coined by the British to propel the Northern fortitude or the project of keeping Nigeria one. Keeping Nigeria one at that time symbolized only the British economic interest and not that of the North¹⁹

On July 6, 1967, federal troops attacked the secessionist region named Biafra, with the order "to penetrate the East Central State and arrest Mr. Ojukwu" (Lt. Col. Ojukwu had been dismissed from the Nigerian Army with ignominy and relieved of his post as Military Governor). To the federal government, it was a "police action to keep Nigeria one" but to the Biafrans who were greatly outclassed by the federal troops in terms of men and materials, it was a genocidal war and the British Propaganda Directorate was to make the outside world believe it was. As the "police action" turned into a full scale war, external forces began to influence the course of the fighting, either in defence or promotion and protection of their individual interests.

As a matter of fact, it was the secession of the Eastern Region from the Nigeria federation that made the civil war totally inevitable.²⁰

i. THE REMOTE CAUSES OF THE CIVIL WAR

The Nigerian civil war which lasted between July 6 1967, and January 12,1970 was fought between the federal government of Nigeria troops and those of the Eastern Region which had unilaterally declared itself the Republic of Biafra. It cost much in men, materials and money. Both soldiers and civilians suffered outrageously particularly within Biafra. Nigeria declared war on Biafra to force the territory's reintegration into Nigeria.

Thus, among the remote causes of the Nigeria-Biafra civil war include the undemocratic amalgamation of different entities and people with different language and different cultures by the British under the name of one country called "Nigeria". This fusion or merging together of two previously different entities by the British was primarily for administrative convenience and uniformity of the British. This means that the British administration did not make an effort to wield the country together and unite the heterogeneous groups of people.

Secondly, inspite of amalgamation, there was no effort to promote national consciousness of oneness. There was no effort towards nation-building. Ethnicity and tribalism was the predominant culture and political attitude which made the federal parliament to be reduced to an intertribal battlefield.

Thirdly, the British encouraged religious differences in favour of the Northern Region. The system of Indirect and Direct Rules produced something like aristocracy or feudalism in the North which is alien to the South. For instance, separate schools were built for the children of the Emirs in the North which those of the common peasants were not admitted. There was no such privileged schools in the South, rather missionary schools were encouraged in the South which was not the case in the North. Add to the above, the opportunistic roles of the politicians, the practice of ethnic politics then known as tribalism and the negative roles of the intellectuals who carried ethnicism into the university system.²¹

ii. THE IMMEDIATE CAUSES OF THE CIVIL WAR

The civil war was preceded by series of crisis, all of which contributed as its immediate causes. Among these were the Action Group (A.G.) crisis

of 1962. This political crisis which erupted in 1962 in Western Nigeria was as a result of disagreement between the leaders of AG, Chief Obafemi Awolowo and his deputy, Chief S.L. Akintola. This crisis in Action Group, described by the Prime Minister as marking "a momentous turning point in our history" demonstrated that in the pursuit of their ambition, the politicians in the First Republic could utterly disregard those conventional practices without which parliamentary democracy is impossible, for example the rule of law and party discipline.

Followed by this is the 1962/63 census controversy. By the word "census" we mean a head count of citizens of a country. Population census enables the government to review their economic and sociopolitical development plans. In Nigeria, it is a politically sensitive issue because population size is taken into account in the delimitation of electoral constituencies and the determination of the formula for sharing federal earned revenue. The 1963 census was believed to have been inflated as it put the population of the Northern Nigeria at 29,758,875 as against 55.6million which was the total population of the entire country. This made the Eastern Nigeria government to challenge

the result in the court, hence the soured relationship between NPC and NCNC.

Another immediate cause of the civil war was the General election crisis in 1964. On December 30, 1964, Nigeria held its first post-independence general election. Unnaturally, the result was in favour of Nigerian National Alliance (NNA). This resulted to crisis, and the crisis was averted that might have broken the federation.

On October 1965, there was another Western House of Assembly election. This election revealed merely, the fragility of the Republic. In this election, the premier of the Northern Region was accused of rigging the election and this resulted to civil disorder. Infact the Western election crisis was certainly the last straw against the democratic experiment of the first Republic.²²

Furthermore, the coup d'etat of January 15,1966 which was later perceived as having an ethnic colour. Otherwise the coup was initially accepted by the vast majority of Nigeria as appropriate solution to the political crisis in the country.

Similarly, the murder of General J. T. U. Aguyi-Ironsi and the systematic liquidation of Igbo military officers and other ranks during their visit to

Ibadan and the emergence of Gowon as the Head of Military Government after the counter-coup of July 29, 1966 was also one of the immediate causes of the civil war. If Ironsi had remained in power, there would have been no civil war.

The non implementation of Aburi Accord by General Gowon and the creation of 12 state structure by the same Gowon's administration without due consultation with the Military Governor of the Eastern Region - Lt. Col. Ojukwu and others. The action which cut the Eastern Region into pieces-making Igbo people minorities in other states and leaving the Igbo heartland land-locked having no outlet to the sea for international trade.

Another immediate cause of the civil war was the organized massacre of Igbo people and Easterners in the North and Lagos - the program and other threats of genocide against the Igbo.

Finally, the height of all was the declaration of the Eastern Region on May 30, 1967 as an independent Republic of Biafra.

Thereafter, General Gowon declared war against Biafra in order to force a reunion with Nigeria.²³

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CHAPTER THREE

THE IMPACTS OF THE NIGERIA-BIAFRA (CIVIL) WAR ON URATTA AND IT'S PEOPLE

The Nigeria-Biafra war which started in 1967 as a result of the bid for the Eastern Region to secede from the rest of the federation did not end until the 12th of January 1970.

The impact was so great as the Eastern region was the theatre of warfare which Uratta community is an integral part of. This war tremendously inflicted much sufferings, devastations, hardship and a total set-back on Uratta people as her economic, political and social activities were paralyzed during this period (1967-1970).

Infact, the consequences of the Nigeria-Biafra war on Uratta are so Catholic and it is as a result of this that the impact will be categorized into: Political and Economic effects.

I. Political Effects

Prior to the outbreak of the Nigeria civil war, the political structure of Uratta community was patterned to meet the needs and aspirations of her people. Usually, the political activities of the Uratta people was

entrusted into the care of the council of Elders who were heads of the compounds, hamlets, or wards. During the Nigerian civil war the council of Elders could not carry out their primary functions of taking decisions on matters affecting the entire community, apportioning punishments on defaulters etc. Political institutions like the Oha, the Amala, the Nze, the Onye Ishi ala, the Oji Ofor, the Onye Ishi Agbara were all in disarray. The functions of the Eze's and his cabinet were halted. Most of the traditional titled men and traditional holders were in hiding for fear of conscription, death or for fear of being accused of collaborating with either the Biafran or Nigerian troops. For instance, one Nze Onyiriogwu Azuwike of Ndokwu Umunahu Uratta was compelled during the war by the Biafran soldiers to take them round Umunahu village so that they can conscript some young Umunahu men to serve in the Biafran Armed Forces. It was therefore as a result of this that made the other titled men in Uratta community to run away to the various neighbouring towns like Uzoagba, Atta etc. thereby abandoning their political duties¹.

It was as a result of the above that political disorder became the order of the day in Uratta community. Nobody was observing the do's and don'ts of the Uratta society. Everybody was doing what he or she likes as none of the council of Elders had time to monitor the activities of the Uratta

people so as to know who was going contrary to the laws or not. This was as a matter of fact the political situation in Uratta during the war period.

Other functions negated were the maintenance of laws, orders, peace, settlement of internal disputes, regulations and performance of rituals aimed at safeguarding the welfare of Uratta people. Also, political institutions like peer group association, pressure group etc were disorganized as a result of the out-break of the war. Some peer group associations disorganized during the war includes: the Ebiriukwu age grade, the Obiwuruotu Social Club of Uratta, the Ezinwanne Age Grade to mention but a few. It is axiomatic that the age grade system has very vital and relevant functions to perform in the political life of any community within the Igbo traditional set up. The age grade was an agent of administration in Uratta community as it decides who goes for what posts in the politics outside or within the Uratta community.

It is in view of the above that Uratta community and her people have since after the war been suffering from all sorts of political domination and humiliation till date. This is because most of the political posts held by the Uratta indigenes in the Nigerian political settings before the war

were taken away from them after the war and given to people from other ethnic groups.

Furthermore, most of the soldiers from Uratta community who served in the Nigeria Army before the war and ran back to the East as a result of the brutality meted on them in the North and oilier parts of the country. During the war, these soldiers fought on the Biafra side, and as a result were not reabsorbed into the Nigerian Army at the end of the war rather they were forcefully retired without benefits or compensation. A good example of such soldier retired at the end of the war without benefit was Late Brigadier P. C. Amadi from Umuiwuala Umunahu Uratta.

Therefore, the war reduced the military personnels of the Uratta indigenes in the today's Nigerian Army. It is a truism to say that after the war, there was mass retirement of the soldiers that fought on the Biafran side some of whom were Uratta indigenes.

The killing of the titled and non-titled elders and the educated elites of Uratta greatly affected the political strength of Uratta people. The educated elites in Uratta who were supposed to educate the young Uratta men and women on the administrative patterns and principles were sent untimely to the great beyond during the war and this has

greatly affected the political activities of Uratta people till date. This is evident in the lack of administrative abilities, wisdom, and efficiency in our (Uratta) today's political representatives. To say the fact, our representatives have no vision, ideology, wisdom and the height of all, programme of action which were obtainable in the per-civil war Uratta political representatives.

The result of this is that Uratta has continually witnessed administrative problems ranging from election malpractice, mismanagement of public fund, embezzlement of public fund and all other forms of political crimes. Those so elected in the political posts now see their political opportunities as an opportunity to break the yoke of poverty in their families and among their friends. Some examples of elders and educated elites of Uratta who were killed during the war includes - Nze Akuwuodo Aharanwa, Oha Anoruo Odii, Mr. Sylvernus Aharanwa, Ichie Nnanna Ofurum to mention just these.

Moreso, so may children who were between the ages of 1 -18 years were equally killed and sent to an untimely grave as a result of the outbreak of the war. These children were supposed to be the future representatives of Uratta community. Some children who died during the war includes: Chimankpa Anosike who was 5 years old during the war,

Kelechi Nnawuihe 9 years old, Akudo Anamelechi 3 year old, Chikodinaka Ekechi 16 years old etc. These Uratta children who were supposed to have been the future generation and representatives of Uratta community were all wasted during the war.

The population of Uratta community as a matter of fact was reduced following the out-break of the war. This is because so many men, women and children lost their lives during this war and this has been affecting Uratta people as population census and population size is taken into account in the delilmination of electoral constituencies and the determination of the formula for sharing federal earned revenue.

Another political effect of the war on Uratta community is that is gave rise to this marginalization question. Today, the political history of Nigeria is Hausa-Fulani dominated. No Uratta indigene is found in any strategic political position in Nigeria.

Finally, the eventual out-break of the Nigerian war (1967-1970) and its aftermath accentuated the Northern bourgeois class at the state power level, while the Yoruba (Western buorgeois class) took great control of the administrative level of the state. The Igbo which Uratta is an integral part of had been engulfed in the civil war of self determination.²

In sum, from the foregoing, it is very correct to say that the political problems in Uratta today sprang up as a result of the civil war which led to the untimely demise of so many of her elders and educated elites who were supposed to impart political knowledge on the young ones (future political representatives)³.

ii. **Economic Effects**

The Nigerian civil war had the Eastern region as the theatre of warfare. The Uratta economic and commercial activities were paralyzed as they plunged in fear, occasionally were lucky to harvest crops.

In the pre-civil war days of Uratta community, her greatest assets were her economic resources. Farming, hunting, animal husbandry and fishing were the dominant occupation of the Uratta people. The Uratta people were respected by their neighbours for their initiative, self-reliance, strength and insatiable thirst for learning. Her relatively large and dense population provided its ready and easy accessible markets for agricultural and industrial products. Thus, some of these markets includes: Ekemegbuoha, Orié Umuorii, Nkwo Umuobaa, Afo Okwu, Nkwo Orji etc. All these markets suffered following the outbreak of the war.⁴

During the Nigeria-Biafra war, agricultural products were destroyed, exploited, stolen and damaged. Some of the agricultural activities were paralyzed, products of the Uratta community that went with the war includes - cassava, yam, maize, palm trees, cocoyam, melon, pumpkin and others. These products were harvested untimely and stolen away by the Owerri Nchi Ise people who ran to Uratta as a result of the war and the Biafran/Nigerian Army.

A great economic effect of the Nigerian civil war on Uratta community was that it led to the decline of agriculture. During the 30 months that the war lasted, agricultural activities were disrupted. Uratta people were no longer going to farm, either for cultivation or for harvestion of her farm products. This resulted to hunger, starvation and malnutrition which consequently led to the out-break of a deadly disease known as kwashiokor. This disease caused as a result of hunger claimed the lives of so many Uratta people especially children during the war. The neglect and decline of agricultural activities in Uratta during the war period paved way for the death of almost al her food crops both those in the farm and those preserved in the barn for future use. This is evident in the words of Mr. Nelson Aharanwa;

"My father used to own a large barn of yam, cocoayam and a little hut where he normally preserves his maize for the next farming season. But following the out-break of the war, my father lost everything to both Uratta indigenes, Owerri Nchi Ise and Egbu refugees and the Biafra/Nigerian soldiers".

Before the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war, yam was the greatest or chief staple food crop in Uratta, but following the emergence of the 30 months war, yam which was the chief crop that was cultivated and harvested annually decayed and was thereafter replaced by cassava. The demise of yam as a result of the Nigeria-Biafra war led to what is tagged today in Uratta as "Cassava Revolution" which simply means that cassava has today taken over the place of yam. In view of the above, one can say that the outbreak of the Nigeria-Biafra war has relegated farming activities in the present Uratta community to the background as she lost all her farm crops during the war.⁵

As earlier cited, Uratta people in the pre-war days involved in animal husbandry. Some of the animals that were trained by the Uratta people includes - goats, dogs, cats, sheep, rams, pigs etc. But with the outbreak of the war, all these were lost, some of these animals died as a result of hunger, some where stolen away and killed by either the Biafrans or the Nigeria troops to serve as food while others ran away to an unknown

destinations. Chickens were not left out in this exercise as they were equally stolen away, and some of them died as a result of bombing by the Nigeria soldiers. According to one Mrs. Eugenia Odii, from Ndokwu Umunahu Uratta, she said that her mother-in-law used to own a lot of cocks and hens but after the war, she could not give an account of her poultry. To say the fact, Uratta people are yet to recover from the set back caused to her agricultural activities as a result of this 30 months war.

Hunting and fishing which were predominantly carried out by Uratta men were put to a halt following the outbreak of the war. Prior to the outbreak of the war, Uratta men engaged in hunting and fishing as part-time job. The products of these activities they sold so as to get money to buy their other necessities.

The emergence of the Nigeria-Biafra war also resulted to loss of job opportunities by most of the Uratta indigenes. Thus, during the massacre of the Igbo in the North and other parts of the country outside the East in 1966, those who survived the brutality ran back to the East to save their dear lives and as a result lost their jobs hence they were not reabsorbed in their respective places of work at the end of the war.

These people includes the Uratta people. Therefore, the Nigeria-Biafra war led to a high rate of unemployment among the Uratta people.

Similarly, the Uratta people who belonged to the Nigerian Army, but following the secession and the outbreak of the war, decided to fight on the side of Biafra were not reabsorbed by the Nigerian Army at the end of the war (1970). As a result, they decided to indulge in buying and selling, and other minial jobs so as to eke out a living. A good example of one of the Uratta sons who was not reabsorbed into the Nigeria Army after the war was late Brigadier P. C. Amadi from Umuiwuala Umunahu Uratta.

Another economic impact of the war or Uratta people was the replacement of the Nigerian currency with the Biafrans currency following the secessions and the change of Biafra currency to Nigeria currency at the end of the war which hitherto rendered the Biafran currency valueless. Biafran currency having been declared worthless seized to be a legal tender and this resulted to poverty, and starvation which consequently inflicted much hardship on the Uratta people. At the end of the war, Gowon's policy on Reconciliation, Rehabilitation and Reconstruction (3^R) which he claimed was geared towards giving the Igbo a means of livelihood after the war, decided to pay the fgbo who

had money in the Banks (those who were able to produce their bank particulars) only the sum of 20pds. (Twenty pounds) irrespective of how huge your money was. This caused a tremendous set back on the Biafran economy as a whole and on Uratta community in particular. Some of the Uratta wealthy men who lost their money as a result of the war includes: Barrister Ejimofor popularly called Jim-Jim, Mr. Jude Madu, Mr. Akujobi Onyeukwu, Mr. Akuwodo Aharanwa, Mr. Evans Ukaga to mention just these. Infact the out-break of the war made these wealthy Uratta men to start life all over again.⁶

Commercial buildings in Uratta community were also destroyed during the war. It is very painful to say that the ugly economic effect of the Nigerian civil war on Uratta is unestimatable. Some markets and shops in Uratta were shelled or bombed down. These commercial buildings includes: Ekemegbuoha market square, Nkwo Orji market and Afo Okwu, Eke Obi market square at Owalla. Regrettably, the money which were supposed to be channelled towards the development of Uratta community was after the war used to rebuild the war damaged markets. Since after the war, till date, Uratta people are yet to recover from the destructive effect of the civil war on her. No wonder the popular saying "war is destructive and not constructive".

Private buildings, schools, churches and hospitals were also damaged and destroyed during the war. Some of the private buildings destroyed includes the house of one Mr. Raphael Ekechi of Umundula Umunahu Uratta. This house was the finest house in Uratta before the war and it was as a result of envy by the Nigerian Army that made them to set this house on fire. St. John's Catholic Primary School Umunahu and St. John's Anglican Primary School Alum-Orii Umunahu were also reduced to the ground during the war. These schools were targeted by the Nigerian Army and bombed down beyond repair. Churches and hospitals were not left out in this exercise. St. Titus Anglican Church Umuobaa was also set on fire by the Nigerian Army during the war. Moreso, Charity Maternity Home Nduhu Umunahu Uratta was equally set on fire during the war. Infact, the Nigerian Army wanted to make sure nothing was left off the Uratta people at the end of the war. Painfully, the scarce resources of the Uratta people at the end of the war was used to reconstruct the war damaged residential buildings, schools, churches and hospitals thereby causing more economic set back on Uratta community.

The last but not the least is that Uratta men and women who were still at their prime and productive ages lost their lives, jobs, and other valuable

items to the war. These human and material resources were supposed to have helped in the rapid development of Uratta community. For instance, Mrs. Utoro Aharanwa of Umunahu Uratta said she lost boxes of her wrapper and some gold jewelries during the war.⁷

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CHAPTER FOUR

OTHER IMPACTS OF THE NIGERIA -BIAFRA WAR ON URATTA

COMMUNITY

War needs no documentation to prove its horrors. It destroys and ruins lives beyond number, it makes anything like normal existence impossible, it imposes immense burden on national economies and imperils the freedom of everyone, it endangers man's very existence on this planet.

War is as old as human history. Pages of history is filled with incidences of war. In fact, war has remained a compicious but disturbing theme in international relations. Wars are fought for divergent reasons. War cannot be wished away in human society. The effect of war is not only the destruction it leaves in its wake, but the shock, hopelessness and the promise of more.

It is also evident that war "destroys, maims, ruins, changes boundaries, topples government, humiliate people, brutalizes the human psyche, wrecks the precious family togetherness, and most regrettably, often sows the seed of other wars.¹

In this vain, one can say that apart from the politico-economic impact of the war on Uratta community, there are still other major impacts. These impacts will be classified under socio-cultural, and positive impacts.

i. SOCIO-CULTURAL EFFECTS

The Nigerian civil war led to the decline of educational activities in Uratta community. Throughout the war period, every school in Uratta was closed down as both teachers and students ran into hiding so as to save their lives. These schools only reopened after the end of the war (1970). This as a matter of fact affected the educational development of Uratta indigenes. Some of the schools that were affected as a result of the war were-St. John's Catholic school Umunahu Uratta, St. Thomas Primary School Owalla Uratta, St. John's Anglican Primary School Alum-Orii Umunahu Uratta and Uratta Secondary School Uratta. These schools were targets of destruction and it was as a result of this that they were bombed and erased to the floor.

Churches and shrines were not left out. So many churches and shrines were abandoned, destroyed and desecrated. People no longer go to churches to worship their God on Sundays and on other week days as both pastors and congregations were on the run. Juju priests were also

on the run for fear of not being conscripted and compelled to go to war. The resultant effect of this is that these holy places were defied as a result of the unworthy and unholy ways which they were used. Some of these churches in Uratta were used as a theatre of rape by both the Biafran and Nigerian soldiers. Most of these holy places in Uratta lost their spiritual strength as a result of their desecration during the war. A good example of a desecrated shrine in Uratta which lost its power (spiritually) was the Amadioha virgin forest located at Amakpakala Nduhu which used to be a strong worship centre for the traditional worshippers before the war.

Healthcare centres were equally destroyed in Uratta as the Nigerian Army wanted to make sure nothing was left of the Igbo (Biafra) which Uratta is an integral part of. For instance are prominent maternity home in Uratta called "Charity Maternity Home" was bombed down by the Nigerian Army. Up till date, that maternity has not been able to be reconstructed. This as a matter of fact made Uratta people who were sick to travel to far places like Uzoagba in search of where to obtain medical treatment. Uratta people suffered this greatly and as a result so many people died on their ways due to proximity.

Following the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war, no marriage ceremonies were observed, burial ceremonies were low keyed and done by only over-aged men and women as the younger ones were on the run. Cultural activities were put to a halt. Festivals, title taking were also brought to an end. Prior to the outbreak of the Nigerian civil war, Uratta people took titles to exhibit their affluence. Some of these titles includes the Nze, Ozo, Ichie, Oha, Eze and the Eze's cabinet. But with the outbreak of the war, such ceremonies were never performed. Some of the elders who already held some cultural posts died as a result of shock, starvation or bombing. The civil war regrettably led to the decline and abandonment of the most important annual festival of Uratta known as "Onwa Oru Uratta".

Traditional dances like Atilogwu, Abigofo, Kele-Kedinma, Alija etc went into oblivion following the outbreak of the civil war. Umediukwu masquerade mainly for young men and elderly men were not carried out through out the war period. Therefore, the psyche and the original culture and traditions of the Uratta people were completely affected and forgotten. To say the truth, the emergence of the Nigerian civil war led to the abandonment of traditional cultures and deities which up till date were never completely reverend

Age-set or Age-grade institutions were also affected. In pre-war Uratta days, males born in the same year or within a specific number of years were grouped together as one age-set. These sets were organized on village basis but each unit could maintain close ties with an identical unit in the neighboring villages. As the war intensified, such institutions never functioned. Nobody was ready to recognize or carry the age set functions since everybody's security was in danger.

Another important social effect of the Nigerian civil war on Uratta community is that it led to forceful marriage of the Uratta women to the Nigerian Army. Those who refused would be brutally murdered. More so, some beautiful and young married ladies were as well forced out of their matrimonial homes only to be remarried by the Nigerian soldiers. Some of these marriages never lasted. The Uratta ladies who were unable to come back home due to one reason or the other were equally sexually abused.²

This is evident in the words of Egbebelu Ugobelu...

There could be no better "Propaganda medium" than the thousands of mutilated bodies and minds that mately or disconsolately found their ways back home (East); the story of gore, the story of mentally and sexually abused women who were

held down while lepers raped them and then stucked their leprosy hands in their mouths.³

For instance, Mrs. Juliana Okoro and Patience Ndukwe all of Uratta community were sexually abused during the civil war period. Moreso, Mrs. Agbazuwaka Anosike and Lydia Konyeha were forcefully married to the Nigerian soldiers and this made their husbands to reject them even when they found their ways home. So many married women were also raped before their husbands. Therefore, the Nigerian civil war gave rise to broken marriages. Similarly, most of these ladies and girls were sexually abused by as many as 2-5 soldiers at a time. Oh! What a wicked way of treating a fellow human being. Some teenagers were also raped during this period which made them to loose their virginity to the Nigerian and Biafran soldiers.

The war also led to refugee problems on Uratta people as a result of it's devastating and destructive nature. Some Uratta indigenes ran to their neighbouring villages where the tempo was not as high as it was in Uratta. With the passage of time, the host communities became very hostile to Uratta people which made some of them to decide to come back to Uratta. On their way, so many of them (men/women) were captured by both the Biafran and Nigerian soldiers. Some who were

captured were killed, raped or taken to the war front. A good example of such hostile village was Uzoagba in the Ikeduru local government area which is a very close neighbour to Umunahu Uratta people. The attitude of this neighbouring village to the Uratta during the war period has as a matter of fact severed the relationship between Uzoagba people and Uratta people up till today.

Furthermore, the civil war also resulted to high rate of corruption, crime, armed robbery and other social menace and immoralities. Perhaps this was as a result of the demobilization of the secessionist troops or perhaps as a result of unemployment. These soldiers who did not surrender their guns at the end of the war thereafter found armed robbery as a lucrative business. For instance, one Charles Onuoha, nicknamed "Captain Blood" and two others were executed for armed robbery in Uratta.

Another resultant effect of the 1967-70 war was that it created three(3) special classes of destitute in Uratta. These are the sick and the unfirm, the poor and the wretched, and the maimed and the amputated.⁴

To sum it all, the socio-cultural effect of the civil war on Uratta community is unestimatable as its impacts are still felt till today.

ii. POSITIVE EFFECTS OF THE WAR ON URATTA

Who is to say that the Nigeria-Biafra war did no "good"? Who is to say that the war produced only evil, that it is never rightfully accepted as a proper course of action, that it did not rescue the oppressed and bring better lives to many people?

Professor James T. Shotwell, one of the great modern crusaders for peace, asserted frankly:

"War--- has been the instrument, great facts of political national history have been established and maintained. It has played a dominant role in nearly all political crisis; it has been used to achieve liberty, to secure democracy, and to attempt to make it secure against the menace of its use by other hands."

Professor Quince Wright developed this same theme "War has been the method actually used for achieving the major political changes of the modern world, the building of nation states, the expansion of modern civilization throughout the world, the changing of the dominant interest of that civilization." It may be superfluous to remind anyone that the great states of modern times have been the product of war, often of many wars.⁵

Therefore, the Nigeria-Biafra war was fought to bring peace, to make for the unity of the country and therefore maintain the territorial integrity of Nigeria as one and indivisible nation. In this vain, the Nigeria-Biafra war is better tagged "the Nigerian war of unity".

War which is regarded as a means of "remedying unjust situations, of settling disputes, of enforcing rights" etc. Therefore, one can say that the Nigeria-Biafra war was fought to correct some of the societal ills inherent in the pre-war days of Nigeria that eventually led to the war.

Uratta (Ndi Igbo) is (are) reintegrated in the words of Ojukwu, in the Nigeria federation with a healthy form of mutual respect and cooperation which was not the case in the pre-war Uratta days.⁶

Due to the fact that the survival of the Igbo was in their hands as was the evidence in the September, 1966 massacre of the Igbo in the North, they (Igbo) were forced to produce their needs which kept them alive throughout the duration of the war. They produced their own arms and ammunitions like rifles, sure battery, explosive, fuel, Ogbunigwe (mass killer). The Igbo (Uratta people) also produced soap, pomade and hair tread which they used during the war. Therefore, the Nigerian civil war

unraveled and boosted the craft and technological advancement of the Igbo people which Uratta is a part of.

Moreso, at the end of the war, a research institute was established by the Federal Military government of Nigeria with the name "Product Development Institute (PRODA)" at Enugu, This institute was designed to enable great scientific innovation created as a result of the exigencies of the war by the Igbo.⁷ This technological advancement and innovations proves that the peoples of Uratta in case of another war can master courage, mobilize and develop their own arms, ammunitions and other materials necessary for human existence without foreign help.

The war also boosted the quantity and quality of the Nigerian Military standard. The war, it can be argued served as an experiment to the Nigerian Army who until now had not witnessed any serious external aggression.

The war also paved way for the recognition of the Nigeria soldiers internationally. This is evident in the enlistment of Nigeria (Uratta) soldiers in the present peace keeping force in Liberia and others in the past. Some of the soldiers from Uratta who fought for Biafra during the 30

months war were thereafter enlisted into the Nigerian Army. For instance Colonial Sylvernus Obioma who was just retired a few years ago.

Another positive effect of the war on Uratta is that it encouraged inter-tribal marriages, that is, between the Nigerians and the Biafrans. So many Uratta ladies were at the end of the war happily married to the Nigerian soldiers. These marriages yielded positive results which resultantly boosted the economic strength of the families involved as their Northern in-laws sent them relief materials like food, cloths, money etc., which helped them to come out of the depression and stress which they could have faced after the war. The war therefore made Uratta people to see themselves, the Northerners and other tribes as one. Some of the Uratta ladies who were and are still married to the Nigerian soldiers are - Mrs. Nduka Useni, who was married to a Nigerian soldier from Kogi State, Mrs. Lidia Konyeha who was married to a Nigerian soldier from Agbor, and Mrs. Angela Yahaya who was also married to a Nigerian soldier from Plateau. All these women mentioned are from Umunahu, Owalla and Umuobaa all in Uratta community.

The replacement of yam with cassava which I labelled the "Cassava Revolution" has turned out to be a blessing in disguise to the people of Uratta. This is because cassava is now in very high demand all over the

country and internationally. Like I said earlier, before the war, yam was the main staple food that fed the entire populace of Uratta. But because of the dislocation of the families and the abandonment of farmland which consequently led to the decline of agriculture and which led to the decay of the yams. The yams having stayed for a whole lot of 30 months of the war without going back to the farms decayed and was eaten up and was subsequently replaced by cassava as the main staple food for the people of Uratta. From the foregoing, one can say that the high demand of cassava locally and internationally has boosted the financial and economic development of Uratta people through the money sold out of it. For instance, Mr and Mrs. Stephen Chikere of Nduhu Umuorii who after the war turned out to be commercial farmers. This husband and wife own hectares of farmlands in Uratta and Umuagwo, Port-Harcourt road where they plant food crops mostly cassava. Today, the man and his wife are seen as one of the wealthy people in Uratta community.

Some of the buildings like schools, health centres, dispensaries and churches that were damaged following the outbreak of the war, were after the war replaced with the help of the United Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF). This organization supplied the needed fund and

materials which was used to rebuild these war damaged facilities. These schools, churches and health care services were replaced or rebuilt to stand the test of time, which was not the case before the war. Good examples include: Uratta Secondary School located at Orié Uratta which has all the modern facilities that make up a Modern Secondary School, Umunahu Primary School was also rebuilt to a better standard after the war. ⁸ Therefore, the war made Uratta people to now see education as a sine qua non in human existence.

Furthermore, the Nigeria-Biafra war led to the demise of so many fetish traditions, cultures and religions and ushered in genuine Christianity.

In a nutshell, the civil war acted as an eye opener to the people and peoples of Uratta community.

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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In 1914, the British Government amalgamated the North and South region into one geo-political entity called Nigeria. This amalgamation was based on the administrative convenience of the British. The merging of the multi nationalities and heterogenous composition of the country signify the difficulty for the working together of the country. Today, Nigeria has over 280 ethnic groups. Therefore, Nigeria is better called nation-state instead of a nation. This is because it is composed of so many ethnic groups that make it up. The margin together of the North and South means that the country Nigeria is a fragile nation state that could break up at anytime and which eventually broke in 1967-70.

On October 1, 1960, the country stumbled to independence after series of constitutional developments and conferences. From here, the various moves taken to enthrone democracy into the country failed. This reason for this was as a result of the political and economic lopsidedness that eventually crumbled the First Republic leading to the first coup and the counter-coup.

Between 1967-1970, the whole of the country (Nigeria) was plunged into a costly, devastating and destructive war between the Eastern Nigeria and the rest of the country.

Before this war and as the Nigerian federation was decaying, various efforts made to bring peace to the country failed. Thus, the atmosphere was set for war and everybody expected war, and eventually there was war. Prior to this time, Colonel Odumegwu Ojukwu the then Governor of the Eastern Region announced publicly his intention supported by the Easterners of their desire to secede. The declaration of the Republic of Biafra tensed up the atmosphere and systemically resulted to the 30 months war.

The Nigerian civil war marked a turning point in Nigeria history. Historians have written many books on the Nigerian civil war and have reached many different conclusions. However, almost all agree that neither the East nor the Nigerian federation wanted the war and none was solely responsible for the war. As we have already seen, Nigerian civilization and development suffered as a result of this war.

Before 6th July, 1967 that the war started, both sides of the warring groups had showed their preparedness for the war as the only way to

peace in order to make sure that it is either the country remaining together or it splits. Therefore, for the Federal government, the need to resist the indivisible nature of the nation, the war was declared to make for peace.

During this war, the money and manpower that could have aided the peaceful development of the country were depleted in this war. To both sides that fought the war, all attention of their various government were concentrated on winning the war which consequently worsened the socio-economic and political development of the nation.

There was arms race for both sides for the need to win the war. This resulted to numerous problems especially on the side of the Igbo who had to fight with their unsophisticated and locally made weapons like ogbunigwe (mass killer), fuel, riffles etc as against the more sophisticated and modern weapons supplied to Nigeria by the super powers like USA, USSR and Britain.

After the end of the war by 12th January 1970, the then military Head of State of Nigeria, General Yakubu Gowon instituted his policy of reconciliation, rehabilitation and reconstruction (3^Rs). This was meant to give the Igbo means of livelihood, since the Eastern Region was the

battlefield. The 3Rs policys went a long way in solving the problems created by the war. Though after every war comes reconstruction, but no amount of reconstruction can solve all the problems created by the war.

Let us realize that the civil war was fought to make sure that the country remains indivisible. Wars are sometimes fought to enable peace reign. This is like the world war 1 which was fought to maintain and ensure that peace reigned in Europe in particular and then entire globe generally. Nigeria has to take this as a challenge and emulate the United States of America which grew as a great nation and attained its industrialization stage after her civil war of 1865.

Today, the hope of the country becoming a great and mighty nation lies in the hands of every Nigerian. Let us equally realise that we have no other country other than this (Nigeria), since the civil war did not divide the country, its indivisible nature lies on us. We should I therefore, learn from history, the mistakes and achievements of the past regimes in Nigeria and outside Nigeria.

For Nigeria to survive as a nation, our leaders must think less of those factors that tend to divide us, and concentrates more on positive factors

which can be used to the advantage of the nation, as great nations like United States of America and others have done.

The laying of the blame of Nigeria's woes at the door of any particular individual or groups is not the present issue. What is important now is to admit that we have serious problems on our hands which require immediate solution before we are all consumed in the self-lit inferno that our present political crisis constitutes. But gloomy as our political firmament may appear, I honestly believe that enduring solutions to the socio-political and economic crisis can still be found.

In this regard, useful lessons can be drawn from countries which at one time or the other had gone through experiences similar to that threatened our co-existence as one nation. My genuine advise is that disintegration should never be allowed to take better part of our psyche as a nation, because disintegration per se may not necessarily offer a genuine and lasting solution towards the oneness of Nigerians nor Biafrans.

Our leaders should be detribalized. This is because Nigeria is not the only multi-ethnic society that has survived as a nation. Britain for one is not a monolithic country. The USA, osterisively the present master of the

world, is far from being a monolithic nation either. The virtues which those countries extol and which have sustained their continued co-existence are genuine democracy, devolution, transparent governance, religious tolerance, rules of law, equity and fair play. These fundamental ingredients of democracy are self-explanatory and need not to be over elaborated. However, the issue of devolutions requires special mention in so far as it is most relevant to our present political crisis. For instance, on paper, with particular reference to Nigeria's made constitution, the country is supposed to be a federation with clearly defined functions for both the central government and state governments. But owing to the prolonged encroachment of the military into the Nigerian's politics, the country has virtually for decades been administered as a unitary polity. In order to diffuse the tension arising from over-centralization of governmental powers, Nigeria has to make a U-turn to its original federation.

To bring about this much desired peace in Nigeria, the government should soften its approach and show a considerable measure of magnanimity by initiating dialogue with a wider spectrum of the wider society. Government deserves the support of all Nigerians. If we have

differences with the government on any particular issue, dialogue should be used to solve this problem rather than confrontation. We should all be used to solve this problem rather than confrontation. We should all engage government constructively on such issues in an atmosphere of peace and understanding devoid of violence and rancour. Therefore, the solution to Nigeria's problems is dialogue and responsive government.

This recommendation proffered, when adopted will make Nigeria to remain as one. What we need in Nigeria is not anything short of -ONE COUNTRY ONE CONSTITUTION, AND ONE DESTINY

Finally, the achievement of these proffered solutions requires full and undivided commitment on the part of all Nigerians. Every administration should be committed to the maintenance of the set objectives and providing an enabling environment for the majority of peace loving Nigerians to achieve these ends, and to applying the law against these intent on it's subversion.

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PART TWO
UNEDITED VERSION OF ORAL INTERVIEWS
MR. ANOSIKE JAMES interviewed on the 27th July, 2011

- KINGSLEY:** (knocks on the door)
- MR. JAMES:** Who is that? Come right in if you are good looking.
- KINGSLEY:** Goodevening sir, and how are you today?
- MR. JAMES:** Am fine today and how are your parents too?
- KINGSLEY:** They are alright
- MR. JAMES:** What can I offer you my son?
- KINGSLEY:** Don't bother yourself papa
- CHRISTY:** Papa, please I've come to find out certain things concerning the Nigeria-Biafra war from you.
- MR. JAMES:** Oh! my son, are you reminding me of that evil war that claimed the life of my mother?
- KINGSLEY:** Am sorry papa
- MR. JAMES:** It's okay my son, What exactly do you want to know about the civil war?
- KINGSLEY:** Papa, please what actually caused the civil war?
- MR. JAMES:** My son, it is a long story. It started in 1966. I just came back from Ghana to come and reside in the village. The next thing I know was that the Hausa are killing the Igbo who are residing there. This made Ojukwu to declare the Eastern Region as a Sovereign Republic of Biafra. It was as a result of this secession that the Hausa people decided to fight the Igbo. Infact, my son, they wanted to finish the Igbo race.
- KINGSLEY:** Is that all papa?
- MR. JAMES:** That is all I can remember

MRS. FELICIA AHARANWA interviewed on the 3rd August, 2011

KINGSLEY: Good evening mama. Are you resting?

MRS. FELICIA: Yes my son. I just came back from my garden and decided to rest before going into the kitchen.

KINGSLEY: Mama Please, am sorry to disturb you by this time of the day but I would like to find out certain thing about the war (civil) from you

MRS. FELICIA: Okay my son. Is it that Ojukwu war?

KINGSLEY: Yes mama

MRS. FELICIA: My son, I don't know what exactly caused the war but all I know was that, that war was caused as a result of selfish leadership by the Hausa people

KINGSLEY: Mama, is that all?

MRS. FELICIA: That is all I know my son.

KINGSLEY: Thank you mama. Good night.

MR. ONWUZURUIGBO MBARA interviewed on the 5TH AUGUST, 2011

KINGSLEY: Papa, good evening. Are you repairing your umbrella?

MR. MBARA: Welcome my son. The rain has spoilt my umbrella so I decided to use it to pass time rather than thinking

KINGSLEY: That is a good decision papa. Papa, please I don't know if it will be convenient for you to give me some information about the cause or causes of the Nigeria-Biafra war?

MR. MBARA: No problem my son. The Hausa people are wicked. They are not supposed to be pitied. They woke up one morning and decided to kill all the Igbo people including the pregnant women living in the North. It was as a result of the Igbo retaliation that they decided to fight us. In fact, my son, you should always pray never to witness that type of war in this your generation

KINGSLEY: Papa, thank you very much and may God bless you.

MR. MBARA: Thank you my son, bye-bye.

MR. PETER OPARARI interviewed on the 6TH AUGUST 2011

KINGSLEY: (knocks on the door)

MRS. PETER: Who is at the door?

KINGSLEY: Good evening mama, my name is me Kingsley Osuji

MRS. PETER: Come in my son

KINGSLEY: Mama good evening, please is papa around?

MRS PETER: Yes he is. I hope there is no problems.

KINGSLEY: There is no problems mama. I've come to see him for something very important.

MRS. PETER: Okay, my son, wait let me go to his room and call him.

KINGSLEY: Thank you ma.

MR. PETER: My son welcome, how are you?

KINGSLEY: Good evening papa. I am alright. Papa please am sorry to disturb your rest.

MR. PETER: There is no problem my son. What is it you want me to do for you?

KINGSLEY: Papa, I was asked by my teacher to find out the cause or causes of the Nigeria-Biafra war, so I decided to come to you.

MR. PETER: Okay my son. You see that war started in 1967 and ended in 1970 after Gowon declared "One Nigeria". The cause of that war was that the Hausa people were killing so many Igbo living in the North. When Ojukwu demanded that Gowon looks into the matter, he (Gowon) refused to take any action on that. It was as a result of that, that Ojukwu decided that there was no point living together as one Nigeria with the Hausa. Thereafter he declared the Eastern region where he was the Governor General, a Republic of Biafra. This made the Hausa to invade the Eastern region thereby

engaging them (Eastern Region) into this 3years war. My daughter, I almost died in that war because I went to the war as a Biafran soldier.

KINGSLEY: Oh papa! Thank you very much. I will be going.

MR. PETER: Won't you wait for my wife to finish cooking?

KINGSLEY: No, thank you sir. Good night.

KINGSLEY: Papa, I was asked by my teacher to find out the cause or causes of the Nigeria-Biafra war, so I decided to come to you.

MR. PETER: Okay my son. You see that war started in 1967 and ended in 1970 after Gowon declared "One Nigeria". The cause of that war was that the Hausa people were killing so many Igbo living in the North. When Ojukwu demanded that Gowon looks into the matter, he (Gowon) refused to take any action on that. It was as a result of that, that Ojukwu decided that there was no point living together as one Nigeria with the Hausa. Thereafter he declared the Eastern region where he was the Governor General, a Republic of Biafra. This made the Hausa to invade the Eastern region thereby engaging them (Eastern Region) into this 3years war. My daughter, I almost died in that war because I went to the war as a Biafran soldier.

KINGSLEY: Oh papa! Thank you very much. I will be going.

MR. PETER: Won't you wait for my wife to finish cooking?

KINGSLEY: No, thank you sir. Good night.

MR. HERBERT ONYEAKAZI interviewed on the 6th August, 2011

KINGSLEY: Good evening, sir.

MR. HERBERT: Good evening my son. Welcome and sit down. Please what can I offer you my dear.

KINGSLEY: Don't worry sir.

MR. HERBERT: If you insist okay

KINGSLEY: Sir, please I've come to find out from you what caused the Nigeria-Biafra war.

MR. HERBERT: My son, I don't think there is any other thing that caused the war other than hatred and envy. My dear, the Hausa hated the Igbo and envied us because of our hard work. It was as a result of this that they decided to kill the Igbo living in the North so that they can wipe the Igbo race and loot their belongings. When the Igbo revenged and decided to stay on their own (secession) the Hausa people therefore declared war against the Igbo.

KINGSLEY: Papa, is this what you feel in your own opinion, caused the war?

MR. HERBERT: Yes my son. That is what I feel. Don't mind what the politicians say caused the war. All of them are criminals.

KINGSLEY: Papa, thank you. Let me be going.